

Effect of Methylphenidate on Blood Glucose Profile in an Adolescent Male with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT Introduction: Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is the most prevalent childhood neurodevelopmental disorder. Methylphenidate (MPH) is a psychostimulant commonly prescribed in clinical practice to treat patients with ADHD. Comorbidity of Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1D) and ADHD in children can be encountered in clinical practice. However, the impact of MPH on the blood glucose profile is scarcely addressed in the literature. **Methods:** Multiple blood glucose concentrations (BGCs) obtained from a 12 years old male with T1D (under treatment with continuous insulin infusion), and comorbid ADHD have been evaluated after having received 2 dose levels (5 mg and 7.5 mg) methylphenidate (MPH). BGCs were assessed at 6 time points, over 3 weeks period. During the assessment periods, the patient had similar daily feeding en activity conditions and unchanged background insulin infusion. The means of the values obtained after each dose level were compared with each other and with those obtained before commencement of MPH treatment (BL). **Results:** Three clinically relevant findings were encountered. The mean values of fasting blood glucose levels (BGLs) obtained during MPH treatment periods were lower than that obtained before MPH use, respectively -28% and -23% below BL for the 5 and 7.5 mg dose levels. The means of other post- MPH treatment values obtained, through the day, were higher than that obtained before treatment, respectively +39% and +40% above BL. Besides, increasing MPH dose level was associated with increased BGL at all assessment time points. **Conclusion:** Methylphenidate seems to dysregulate blood glucose levels in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus. This might lead to severe consequences, including both microvascular and macrovascular diseases, particularly in vulnerable subjects such as those who receive medication for a long period. Commencement of treatment with and up-titration of MPH dose in ADHD patients with comorbid T1D requires close monitoring of blood glucose concentrations to avoid potential blood glucose excursions that might lead to unwanted complications.

KEYWORDS Methylphenidate, ADHD, Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus

Introduction

Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is the most prevalent childhood neurodevelopmental disorder. Worldwide, an estimated mean prevalence of 7.2% (95% confidence interval: 6.7 to 7.8) in children and adolescents aged 18 and under has been reported [1,2].

Methylphenidate (MPH) is a psychostimulant commonly prescribed in clinical practice to treat patients with ADHD. It improves the cognitive processes, attentiveness and concentration

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through antagonism of dopamine and norepinephrine transporters. Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1D) is the most prevalent type of diabetes in children and adolescent. It is characterized by autoimmune destruction of pancreatic beta cells resulting in deficiency of insulin secretion. In Europe an estimated prevalence of 59,9 (in Italy) to 427,5 (in Finland) per 100,000 children (0-14 years of age) has been reported [3].

Comorbidity of T1D and ADHD in children can be encountered in clinical practice. Kapellen et al. [4] found 4.2% of children with T1D to have ADHD. In the same report, overall prevalence of children who received both drugs for the treatment of ADHD and insulin was 2.9%.

Dysregulation of glucose homeostasis in T1D can cause short- and long-term dysfunction and damage of many organs including retinopathies and nephropathies that could commence within five years of disease onset [5]. Nevertheless, the impact of MPH on the blood glucose profile is scarcely addressed in the literature.

Methods

This report is about a 12 years old male patient who has eight years history of T1D and is wearing an insulin infusion pump to regulate his BGC. The insulin pump provides a continuous and steady dose of basal and, upon patient's request, a postprandial bolus of insulin. He has been referred to the community child and adolescent mental health service, Northern Netherlands because of forgetfulness, inattentiveness, and impulsive and hyperactive behaviour that resulted in infrequent self-monitoring and poor diabetes management. After establishing a diagnosis of ADHD, he received immediate-release MPH at a twice-daily dose (at 08:00 and 12:00 hr.) of 5mg (1-week treatment) up-titrated to a 7.5 mg.

BGCs were checked at six-time points over a period of 3 weeks (one week in which the patient received BID 5 mg and two weeks in which he received BID 7.5 mg), 08:00 hr. (premedication, fasting sample), 09:00hr (1hr after the first dose), 12:00 hr. (before second dose), 13:00 hr. (1hr post-second dose), 18:00hr (before dinner) and 21:00hr. Also, BGCs recorded on the insulin pump during one week before receiving MPH (baseline, BL, values) were tracked for comparison. Time points at which six or more BL values were available have been used for comparison. These were at three-time points: 08:00, 18:00 and 21:00 hr.

Throughout the four weeks assessment period (one BL week and three treatment weeks) the patient had similar daily feeding en activity conditions and unchanged background insulin infusion.

The means of the values obtained were used for comparison. The effect of MPH on his behaviour and compliance with his diabetes management through frequent self-monitoring of BGC were also evaluated.

Results

The means of individual values are demonstrated in table 1 and figure 1. Three main findings.

Firstly, the mean of values obtained at 18:00 hr. after 5 and 7.5 mg dose were higher than that of values obtained before treatment with MPH (BL), respectively +39% and +40% above BL.

Secondly, mean values of fasting BGCs obtained during MPH treatment periods were lower than that obtained before MPH use, respectively -28% and -23% below BL for the 5 and 7.5

Pre= Before treatment with methylphenidate

mg dose levels. In this context, the difference between fasting BGCs means after the 5, and 7.5 mg dose levels was 0.6 mmol/l (ca. 5%), which could be considered as a clinically irrelevant difference being within 1SD of the mean variability of both 5 mg and 7.5 mg dose levels, see table 1.

Thirdly, increasing MPH dose level was associated with increased BGCs at all assessment time points.

Regarding his behaviour and compliance, these were significantly improved after the 7.5 mg dose level. The patient indicated improvement in his concentration, attention and impulsive behaviour which resulted in adequate self-monitoring.

Giving the observed impact of MPH on the BGCs, particularly trends of increased blood glucose levels through the day, the subject was referred back to his diabetic care physician for review and adjustment of the basal insulin dose.

Discussion

In this report, we used the means of multiple diurnal blood glucose values obtained at the same time, at six-time points. This helps assessment of the central tendency and variability of glucose levels over time [6]. The mean blood glucose level has been reported to be a better predictor (than individual variability in blood glucose levels) of poor glycemic control that leads to development and progression of microvascular diabetes complications [6]. As in previous reports [7] blood glucose levels were assessed at 1-hour post-dose which is the time about which peak levels could be expected.

This report describes 3 clinically meaningful findings. First, post methylphenidate increase in blood glucose level as compared to BL. In this context, our finding is not in line with an earlier report [8] that suggested an MPH- induced decrease in serum glucose level in an adult female patient with type 2 Diabetes mellitus (T2D). However, the patient in that report (T2D patient) had been receiving glipizide for her disease. The author has proposed a drug-drug interaction as a potential mechanism for the finding. Our patient is a T1D patient who receives nothing but insulin to manage his disease. Previous reports have shown that MPH significantly increase blood epinephrine concentrations [9,10]. This leads to stimulation of all adrenergic receptors, including α 1 adrenergic receptors (α 1ARs), β ARs and α 2ARs on pancreatic β -cells. On the one hand, stimulation of α 1 ARs, B-ARs is associated with release of gluconeogenic precursors from skeletal muscle, increased pancreatic glucagon

Table 1

Assessment period	Assessment time					
	08:00hr	09:00hr	12:00hr	13:00hr	18:00hr	21:00hr
BL	*(14.9: 3.2)/6	-	-	-	(9.2: 4.8)/6	(10.4:5.4)/7
5 mg MPH	(10.8:3.7)/7	(12:5.4)/6	(8.3:3.5)/7	(9.94:3.8)/6	(12.5: 3.9)/6	(7.14: 3.1)/6
7.5 mg MPH	(11.4:2.9)/13	(12.4:3.8)/13	(14.4:3.5)/13	(13.7:3.8)/13	(12.9: 3)/13	(10.8:4.4)/13

*Mean, SD (mmol/l) and number of BGCs obtained at BL and during the 5mg and 7.5 mg treatment periods.

secretion, and increase in liver glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis with decrease in glycogenesis [11]. On the other hand, in non-T1D patients with functioning pancreatic α cells (which is not the case in this patient), stimulation of α 2ARs, on pancreatic - suppresses insulin secretion in both experimental animals and human [11,12]. Taken all together, increased plasma epinephrine will lead to increase in blood glucose level.

Interestingly, the patient in this report doesn't have functioning pancreatic beta cells. Therefore the observed increase in blood glucose concentrations reflects the process of glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis, either directly or via increased glucagon secretion. Secondly, MPH caused a dose-related increase in blood glucose. This finding has been previously reported in experimental animals where epinephrine caused a dose-dependent stimulation of the rate of glucose formation in both obese and lean rat hepatocytes [13]. In clinical practice the starting dose of MPH in children and adolescent with ADHD is usually 5 mg orally twice a day, to be increased gradually according to the patient's clinical response, up to a maximum dose of 60 mg/day. This usually happens without monitoring of blood glucose level. In T1D, a blood glucose level exceeding ten mmol/l is considered hyperglycemia [14]. Long-term glucose excursions beyond this threshold may pass unnoticed and ultimately might lead to severe consequences. Given this, regular close monitoring is required during MPH dose up-titration. Thirdly, There was a decrease in the means of fasting blood concentrations obtained after MPH administration compared to the mean of values obtained before MPH treatment, respectively -28% and -23% for the 5 and 7.5 mg dose levels. This might be explained by partial adrenergic receptor desensitization and decreased gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis during the overnight fast. Seven hours exposure of α 1ARs to catecholamine has been previously reported to cause 10-fold loss in sensitivity of α 1ARs to catecholamine [15]. This finding would be relevant to consider in diabetic patients who have well-controlled blood glucose profile. The decrease in overnight blood glucose levels may unnecessarily expose patients to hypoglycemic levels which are commonly encountered in T1D patients.

In conclusion, prescribing clinicians need to be aware of the effect of MPH on blood glucose profile in patients with T1D. This may help avoidance of dysregulation in glucose homeostasis that might end up in long-term dysfunction and damage of vital organs. Further investigations to confirm the findings in this report are warranted.

Competing Interests

The authors declared that this report was done independently without any conflict of interest of any organizations that would

lead this review to bias.

Authors' contributions

Khalid Abou Farha is involved in the pharmacological treatment of the patient, reported the findings and had primary responsibility for drafting this manuscript. Ramy Abou Farha was actively involved in evaluation of the findings and has revised this article for important intellectual content. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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